

IPBES VA Chapter 4 - Literature review on outcomes in environmental certification / IPBES values assessment

4.5

Code: IPBES_VA_4.5

Versioning 01: (01.12.2020)

Versioning 02: (02.05.2022)

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4394498

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Description

The IPBES Scoping document for the values assessment highlights the need to assess the types of values of nature that have (or have not) been incorporated into decision-making, the types of valuation approaches incorporated into decision-making, the challenges that have hindered the incorporation of diverse conceptualizations of values of nature in a range of decision and policymaking contexts and the implications for different stakeholders. In this context a literature review was conducted to examine how values are articulated in environmental certification schemes by diverse stakeholders. Through this review we address the following questions:

- What are the states of sustainability certifications programs for various agricultural commodities, with the focus of commodities that have high economical values and are export oriented?
- How decisions among sustainability certifications are influenced by stakeholders relevant to each supply chain of the commodities?
- What values are involved, by whom, and what are the relationships between value articulation approaches (implicit and explicit) that support decisions towards sustainability certifications and 'desired' outcomes? Are there any contested values among stakeholders?

Process overview

Protocol:

We conducted a review of review papers on environmental certification associated with different commodities and with recognizable outcomes on ecosystems or people.

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Literature review of review papers
- **Search language:** English
- **Search engine:** Google Scholar
- **Search terms:**
 - TS=("certification*" AND "sustainability" AND (Oil Palm OR Palm OR Cocoa OR Coffee OR Fish OR Soybeans OR Timber) OR (responsibility OR impact* OR valu* perception OR preferences) AND (Farmer, smallholder)
Refined by: "review"
 - TS=("certification*" AND "sustainability" AND (Oil Palm OR Palm OR Cocoa OR Coffee OR Fish OR Soybeans OR Timber) OR (responsibility OR impact* OR valu* perception OR preferences) AND (Consumer)
Refined by: "review"
 - TS=("certification*" AND "sustainability" AND (Oil Palm OR Palm OR Cocoa OR Coffee OR Fish OR Soybeans OR Timber) OR (responsibility OR impact* OR valu* perception OR preferences) AND (Corporate, company, firm, agribusiness)
Refined by: "review"
- **Sample extracted:** 78 papers (13 on oil palm, 19 on cocoa, 13 on coffee, 12 on fish, 8 on soybeans and 13 on timber)
- **Fields extracted (A):**
 - Citation
 - Commodity
- **Location and format of the data (A):** IPBES_VA_4.5_2020_(A).csv

Further papers were included in the review in order to have evidence that relates certification schemes to methods for measuring their impact. These additional papers were obtained through expert recommendation.

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Incorporation of additional literature through expert knowledge
- **Sample extracted:** 41 papers
- **Fields extracted (B):**
 - Study
 - Authors
 - Year
- **Location and format of the data (B):** IPBES_VA_4.5_2020_(B).csv

Treatment applied: Based on expert knowledge, the 119 papers were screened and the final set of papers to inform chapter 4 was obtained.

- **Sample extracted:** 95 papers
- **Fields extracted (C):**
 - Source
 - Study

- DOI/Link
- Journal
- Authors
- 1st Author
- Year
- **Location and format of the data (C):** IPBES_VA_4.5_2020_(C).csv

Treatment applied: Analysis of the literature. Studies in **(C)** were reviewed to identify outcomes of certification schemes and the role of values and valuation in relation to the policy tool. Key variables identified included the analysis of outcomes in relation to :

- Basic needs
- Physical infrastructure
- Fairness, social infrastructure
- Ecological infrastructure
- Political economy
- Institutional aspects (participation, politics, power, procedural justice, land tenure rights)
- Socio-cultural aspects (values, knowledge, crowding, social cohesion, recognition of justice)
- Livelihoods (income/poverty, equity, food security, well-being, distributive justice)
- Environmental aspects (ecosystem services, effectiveness, efficiency, biodiversity offsite/leakage)

Results from this review are presented in chapter 4 in section 4.5.4.

Definition of files

ID	Name	File Type	Size	Description
A	IPBES_VA_4.5_2020_(A)	csv	17 KB	Sample of 78 papers obtained by performing searches in Google Scholar
B	IPBES_VA_4.5_2020_(B)	csv	6 KB	Sample of 41 papers obtained through expert recommendation
C	IPBES_VA_4.5_2020_(C)	csv	22 KB	Final set of 95 papers used for the analysis of literature